

PRIORITY TASKS OF PERSONAL SPIRITUALITY IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE NEW DEVELOPMENT STRATEGY OF UZBEKISTAN

Teshaboev Akram Yuldashevich

Associated Professor, Head of the Department of Pedagogy and Psychology, Andijan State
Institute of Foreign Languages

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7743088>

Abstract. *In the process of improving the mechanisms of communication with the people, by further improving the mechanisms of open communication with the people, expanding the practice of making important decisions, taking into account public opinion, the spiritual improvement of a person depends on his spiritual wealth.*

Keywords: *spirituality, integrity, personality, society, pedagogy, psychology, development strategy, ideology, idea.*

The process of improving the mechanisms of communication with the people, by further improving the mechanisms of open communication with the people, expanding the practice of making important decisions taking into account public opinion, the spiritual maturity of a person depends on his spiritual wealth. Therefore, as long as there is life, as long as there are countries, states and their interests, they strive to determine the path of development, the horizons of tomorrow through their national idea, national ideology. Etymologies of the terms idea, ideology, national idea, national ideology, and spirituality confirm these thoughts of our President.

Spiritually – this word is derived from the Arabic words "ma'no" or "ma'waniyatun", "manoi goya" and means "mental state".

Idea - it consists of processes, works, future plans and principles based on the good intentions and thoughts of people.

Ideology – it consists of the spiritual-scientific system of people's relations with the state, society, the people, the world and their development in the period of a certain regime.

National ideology – it consists of a system of relations with the state, society, the world, each other, development, based on the spiritual-scientific mentality and ideas of our people.

Our goal is to achieve a prosperous life for our people on the basis of an independent, legal democratic state and a free civil society. Freedom of thought and activity is actually based on the rarity and uniqueness of man. Because the realization of human continuity begins with the realization of its rarity and uniqueness. Understanding the rarity and uniqueness of a person, firstly, forms the basis for realizing the possibilities hidden in him and forms the desire, and secondly, it causes respect and glorification of people through the understanding of the unique and great personality of others. Thirdly, believing that others are also rare and unique, respecting them cleanses the soul from prejudice. Fourthly, based on the realization of the uniqueness of each person, it is a natural necessity for human society to acquire material, scientific, spiritual and cultural benefits of dealing and interacting with others. The formation of the above qualities is the basis of perfection qualities.

In order to continuously form the qualities of perfection, only advices and invitations are not enough. When a person's spiritual activity is matched with practical and professional activity, the qualities of perfection are naturally formed and developed. It is the correct understanding of the above concepts that helps to choose the right methodological bases of education. Because the subjectivity, democratic, legal, humane basis of education is to realize the rare and unique features of people.

The above qualities are the components of human spirituality. When it comes to the fact that the maintenance of the spirituality of people is the second priority direction of the improvement of our society, I first of all imagine a powerful inner force that invites a person to spiritual purification and elevation, enriches the inner world of a person, strengthens his faith and belief, and awakens his creativity. they gave

Every human being is created with full potential for a perfect life. But everyone has their own learning, abilities and opportunities. So, if everyone can find his personal way of life, then his life will be bright, his work will be creative, his work will be fruitful and useful. A person actually achieves true happiness in the process of cocktails. Because if he finds his way of life, he will start winning in his personal creative participation. At this time, he is given spiritual support in absentia, material and spiritual creativity, his promising new ideas start to invite him to practical and creative ways. Therefore, parents, family members, kindergartens, schools, and general educational institutions are responsible for each child's learning, interests, and abilities. It is morally necessary to explain the rarity and uniqueness of people to students and young people in accordance with worldly religious sciences. At this time, young people consciously understand that some non-religious currents are actually unscientific. If a person can find the path of his life, if his mind can develop independently and fall into the direction of the subconscious, then, like the matching of interpretations, a spiritual and spiritual harmony will occur in a person, and he will enter the path of perfect perfection.

Consciousness and subconsciousness are carried out with the help of conscience. It is a spiritual-human feeling, a quality that balances the mind, subconsciousness and heart of conscientious people. If it is necessary to explain conscience in a simple way, then conscience is the spiritual criterion of the actions (activity) performed by the soul.

It is not in vain that our wise people, our forefathers said, "May God be in your heart, my child." Therefore, in the main sources, conscience is said to be the god in the heart of each person. From time to time, a person gives an account of his actions in front of his conscience. This communication should be a genuine communication. Sometimes proving a wrong thing as right is as strong as cheating one's conscience, and that is cheating God. In this case, the subconscious (reality) comes into play, and an imbalance between the mind and the subconscious begins, leading to a mental illness. Mental illness leads to physical illness, and in some cases it can lead to other unfortunate events.

SUBCONSCIOUS (Mindset). Spiritual and spiritual way of human personal activity based on worldly and vital reality.

HUMAN MIND - it is the level of spiritual perspective activity based on his perception, understanding of life and worldly reality.

COMPREHENSION – perceiving a truth verbally, spiritually and mentally.

HUMAN THOUGHT based on his consciousness and perception, observational activity in life and worldly things and processes.

INTELLEGENCE it is to understand worldly and vital truths based on one's own perception, heart and mind and to follow them in one's activities from a spiritual and human point of view.

HUMAN HEART a force that urges a person to emotional and practical activity based on the unity of personal consciousness and spirituality. It adapts to the conscience, mind, and thoughts, and becomes the gaze, fall, and strength of the soul.

HUMAN SOUL It is a spiritual force that can take a person out of all kinds of difficulties and lead him to great good deeds.

Although we have tried to understand these spiritual and spiritual qualities by defining them separately, they are in fact inextricably linked. First of all, a person is a spiritual and spiritual figure. Therefore, a person should derive spiritual and human satisfaction from his every work. Spiritual and human satisfaction occurs from the harmony of mind, soul, spirit and activity. This is an internal compatibility that is unique to each person. Internal fit leads to job satisfaction. He will be pleased with himself. Internal spiritual-spiritual harmony is the basis of biological-physiological life harmony in a person. This, in turn, is the health of the body and the freshness of the spirit. It greatly helps the internal harmonic balance in a person. Because a person is closely connected with the external spiritual and spiritual world, and in fact is an inseparable part of it.

A person is harmoniously connected with the entire spiritual-spiritual world, the universe, and this connection is always in spiritual-spiritual balance.

The spiritual structure of light is **SCIENCE, INTELLIGENCE, WISDOM, PRIDE, ENLIGHTENMENT AND ENLIGHTENMENT**. Therefore, people who are not just light for people like the whole world, but who embody constant spirituality and forgiveness and follow it in their activities are called enlightened people. Yes, such people really shine. This light has spiritual and spiritual qualities invisible to autumn.

The structure of the qualities of light, light, white, purple, airy, green, yellow, fire, and red colors, coming from the universe, connects the seven worlds and humanity, the material world.

You have observed the seven colors of the rainbow several times in nature. Each color of the rainbow is the color of the seven heavens, and the color of white light ensures the harmonious unity of the whole universe with their complex orca. Similarly, each of the seven heavens has a corresponding musical sound. The material world, humanity is organically and harmoniously connected with another spiritual-spiritual quality.

Metabolism, life process in the material-physical body of a person is inextricably linked with his spiritual-energetic body. The level of development of the material-physical body depends on the level of development of the spiritual-energetic body. The material-physical body consists of matter and spiritual-emotional parts. The spiritual-emotional part is the structural part of the spiritual-energetic body, it is harmoniously connected with the heavens of the universe. One of the structural foundations of the spiritual-emotional part of the body is the human heart. Since the heart is the force that motivates a person to emotional and practical activity based on the unity of consciousness and spirituality of a person, its purity is related to the human conscience. Conscience is a personal feeling that responds to the subconscious divine power for its activity.

Every person has his own education, abilities and character, and his rarity and uniqueness are proven by modern humanities. So, the first guarantee of achievements and successes is the

choice of activity, life style, profession, according to each person's education, abilities and interests. The second guarantee of success is to act with wisdom, reason, and get the most material and spiritual products from the chosen way of life. Working with the mind is thinking positively about the field one is occupying. Yes, a positive spiritual mind in this field is the third guarantee of human achievement. If the soul is not filled with purity and good intentions, the development of consciousness and thought cannot go beyond the third bioenergetic body. If the heart of desires and desires is pure and devoted to good intentions, then the spiritual-spiritual body (subconscious) will be activated, and the balance of consciousness and subconsciousness will be formed. In this case, a person's bioenergetic power is optimized, gets great strength and power, and the gate of unseen qualities is opened to such people.

Material and spiritual productivity is related to the mental and practical perfection of a person. it opens the way to discoveries, innovations, new technologies, technical product ideas. Regardless of the field of activity, the bioenergetic body will not work at all, if the activity of a farmer, laborer, carpenter, servant is not expected to reach high levels of practical-creative, spiritual productivity. If the bioenergetic body does not work properly, it starts to hinder the spiritual and spiritual development of the body, which, in turn, hinders its physical development. Lack of spiritual and physical development hinders spiritual and spiritual growth, when a person does not fulfill his essence, the imbalance of consciousness and subconsciousness begins, and a person's mood of dissatisfaction arises. Then he starts to wear artificial furs to cheer up his mood. This leads to alcoholism, smoking, drug addiction, drug addiction, domestic disorders. The natural factor of prevention of these social evils is to reveal the true nature of a person and make him use his enormous material and spiritual capabilities and power. Because a person who, on the basis of his education and realization of his abilities, creates material and spiritual products, feeds himself and his family with pure and honest food, and serves to enrich the state and people materially and spiritually, becomes a true believer not only in words, but also in practice.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 dated 28.01.2022. N: PD-60.
2. Development strategy of new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026
3. Work to be carried out in the Namangan region within the framework of the State program for the implementation of the development strategy of the new Uzbekistan for 2022-2026 in the "Year of glorifying human dignity and active neighborhood". https://www.namangan.uz/images/dastur-2022-2026-dekabr_oyi.pdf
4. A. Avloni. Turkish Gulistan or ethics. T. 1996.
5. A.R. Beruni. In terms of spirituality and education. T. 1992.6.
6. Басов, Н.Ф. Социальная педагогика. Учебное пособие для ВУЗов / Н.Ф. Басов. - М.: КноРус, 2018. - 230 с.
7. Гагарин, А.В. Психология и педагогика высшей школы. Курс лекций, учебно-методические материалы и рекомендации, рабочие тетради / А.В. Гагарин. - М.: МЭИ, 2016. - 240 с.

8. Дивногорцева, С.Ю. Теоретическая педагогика. В 2-х т. Т. 2. Теория обучения. Управление образовательными системами: Учебное пособие / С.Ю. Дивногорцева. - М.: ПСТГУ, 2017. - 262 с
9. Gaybullaev N.R., Yodgorov R., Zhdarkin L.P., Tashmurodova Q., Mamatkulova R., Akhrorova Z., Ruzimatov E. Social reforms and education. T. 1995.